

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D3.5 Online Masterclasses

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
Q&A	Questions and Answers

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Executive Summary

The Capacity-building Flagship Programme of the AfriConEU Networking Academy, as overviewed in *D3.1 - Capacity Building Flagship Programme*, is composed of four sub-programmes, each one comprising the delivery of different activities. In total, the 4 sub-programmes will organize 12 workshops, 20 webinars and 8 masterclasses, complemented with additional resources that will be available in the online repository in the AfriConEU repository.

This deliverable (D3.5) seeks to offer a complete guide for organizing the masterclasses, meeting the needs of local DIHs. This document outlines the masterclasses' specific details, including the main objective and expected learning outcome, content, thematic focus, material, and profile of invited lecturers.

The masterclasses are expected to be interactive and learner-centred to drive the interest of the representatives of the African DIHs. The masterclasses address the conclusions included in *D2.1 – State of play in African DIHs: The case of Ghana, Nigeria, Tanzania and Uganda*, *D2.2. – Online database with DIHs Capacity Building Programmes* and *D2.3 - Lessons from existing initiatives and good practices for enforcing DIHs capacities*.

Based on the analysis of these conclusions, the masterclasses will cover 8 key areas, as follows:

- Sustainable business development, lessons learnt
- Business strategy development for DIHs, lessons learnt
- Lessons from European start-ups
- Business Intelligence and Analytics
- Essentials of innovation finance
- Financing digital innovation hubs
- Gender-lens Finance – Bridging the gender finance gap
- Building a Theory of Change

Introduction

The AfriConEU Capacity Building Programme aims to enhance the capacities of African DIHs to better serve their own needs and long-term sustainability and the needs of local SMEs, start-ups, and young people, with a keen emphasis on women and people from marginalized backgrounds.

The AfriconEU Networking Academy has two flagship programmes: i) Capacity Building for African DIHs; and ii) Partnership Building between African and European DIHs. Masterclasses, as discussed in this document, fall under the Capacity Building flagship programme which has the following sub-programmes:

1. Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach;
2. Capacity building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.);
3. Capacity building on start-up's financial support;
4. Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women.

One or more consortium partners are designing each subprogramme. The [Innovation Technology Cluster](#) (ITC) from Slovenia is designing the first programme, [Porto Business School](#) (PBS) from Portugal the second one, [DPixel](#) from Italy the third one, and lastly, the fourth one is being designed by the [African Technology Business Network](#) (ATBN) from the United Kingdom, [Youthmakers Hub](#) (YMH) from Greece and PBS.

The partners leading the development of the training materials do not aim to design entirely new concepts but to utilize existing materials and capitalize on achievements and lessons learned from previous and ongoing relevant initiatives.

This deliverable focuses on the structure and training material for the masterclasses. The selected themes, structure and training approaches were designed based on the research outcomes and need assessment conducted under WP2 by ATBN and ITC in the African ecosystem, in particular *D2.1 – State of play in African DIHs: The case of Ghana, Nigeria, Tanzania and Uganda*. According to D2.1, African DIHs are facing several challenges, lack of core funding, sustainable business models and more diversified and sustainable revenue streams, in-depth business development expertise in key areas, capacity in facilitating investment, knowledge in gender-related issues, development of effective ecosystem-wide partnerships, data to back up recommendations that DIHs are making to policy-makers, knowledge to invest in start-ups and standardized offer. The masterclasses' thematic areas were also selected based on the opportunities for knowledge exchange from European to

African DIHs as identified in WP2 under D2.2. – *Online database with DIHs Capacity Building Programmes*. The deliver D2.3 - *Lessons from existing initiatives and good practices for enforcing DIHs capacities* also gives relevant insights on the needs of DIHs that should be further addressed, such as additional knowledge on networking, strategy and business development, and guidance on service portfolio and communication and awareness creation. D2.3 also stressed the preferences of DIHs concerning the format of e-learning activities: DIHs tend to prefer shorter online programmes and more interactive programmes. These insights are followed in the outline of the online masterclasses.

Based on the needs and preferences identified, the AfriConEU masterclasses will cover 8 key areas(2 per sub-programme), as follows:

Sub-Programmes of AfriConEU Capacity Building Flagship Programme	Masterclasses
1. Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable business development, lessons learnt • Business strategy development for DIHs, lessons learnt
2. Capacity building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.);	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lessons from European start-ups • Business Intelligence and Analytics
3. Capacity building on start-up's financial support;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essentials of innovation finance • Financing digital innovation hubs
4. Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender-lens Finance – Bridging the gender finance gap • Building a Theory of Change

The masterclasses will be led by local facilitators selected with the support of the African partners.

All the teaching materials developed under the D3.5 and links to other existing relevant materials will be uploaded into the online repository at the AfriConEU website for easy access. The structure and the materials that now are being conceptualized will be implemented in WP4's activities.

To ensure continued support and improvement on African- European partnerships in the DIH ecosystems, several European DIHs will be used as mentors to support the African DIHs that participate in the masterclasses.

The analysis of this document should be complemented with the study of the D3.7 - *Capacity Building Flagship Programme*, as it includes the overall structure of the D3.5 Online Masterclasses www.africon.eu

Capacity Building Programme. Additionally, because the responsible partners for elaborating D3.5 are not the only ones who will implement the AfriConEU programmes, it was decided to keep the materials open, flexible and adaptable to fit various methods and approaches (in line to what is being decided to the other materials presented in D3.1, *D3.2 - Structure and training material for local workshops*; *D3.3 - Webinars Content and Design*; *D3.4 - Inventory of capacity building resources and ready to use training material*).

Chapter 1. Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach

Masterclass #1: Sustainable business development, lessons learnt

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

Digitalization and sustainability are two key challenges in business. The main objective of the masterclasses is to explore business opportunities when DIHs align their strategy with sustainability goals. The participant will understand the sustainable context framework, the methods and tools for addressing sustainable challenges, how digital technologies can help manage and innovate their role in the business ecosystem and support sustainable development and the existing digitally-enabled sustainable solutions.

CONTENT

Sustainable solutions and integration of sustainability into the business through sustainable development opportunities and why we need sustainable development.

THEMATIC FOCUS

This masterclass will focus on integrating sustainability into businesses as a central part of their way of doing business to increase profitability. As the market changes and customers and society search for more sustainable solutions, new sustainable opportunities arise, so we need to understand the broader system along the current and future value chain and transform it beyond the regulatory framework and ensure that ambitions are sustainable and valuable for the organizations as well as for the broader scope.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, Examples from case studies, canvases for sustainable business models, best practice examples from DIH. The lecturer will prepare these materials and upload them onto the online repository.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Sustainability expert, circular economy expert, practitioners on the field of sustainable business development

Masterclass #2: Business strategy development for DIHs, lessons learnt

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

Participants will learn key success factors for their business strategy, developing their DIH's value proposition through their services and customers' needs and demand. They will identify their organization's core competencies and develop their mission and vision, which will be the base for defining DIHs value propositions.

Learning outcome: business canvas, defining DIHs value proposition and services.

CONTENT

Participants will learn 10 steps to their business strategy, overview, trends and customer needs, competitor and technology, and the 4 pillars of business strategy. The second part will learn about the value proposition, how they can develop it through their services, define DIH's customer needs and demand, align with offered services, and improve.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Developing their business strategy takes 10 steps, from trends, customer needs, competitor and technology watch, ambition, innovation life cycles, competency assessment, vision and mission, search field, competence roadmap to the business case.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, Examples from case studies, canvases for sustainable business models, best practice examples from DIH. These materials shall be prepared by the lecturer and uploaded onto an online repository.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Business model and strategy specialist, experience with working with DIHs

Chapter 2. Capacity Building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.)

Masterclass #3: Lessons from European start-ups

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

Participants will learn key success factors of European start-ups to take the African start-up economy to the next level.

CONTENT

By introducing fundamental subjects such as access to talent, finance and public policy aspects (insights for data-driven policy-making) that drove Europe into a unified market, African DIHs and start-ups will acquire insights significant towards start-up growth and development of a common market. European start-ups are indeed being created and growing at an unprecedented pace, attracting the attention of global investors, customers, and corporate partners alike so that several lessons could be exploited.

The ultimate goal is to build a community of innovators between Europe and Africa and understand how collaborations could be fostered.

THEMATIC FOCUS

European start-ups; network; challenges; opportunities; public policy; talent; finance; collaborative platforms

MATERIAL

Powerpoint presentations; polls; additional materials.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Entrepreneurship experts; start-up creation experts; sustainable development experts; business strategy experts; innovation managers

Masterclass #4: Business Intelligence and Analytics

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

During this masterclass, participants will acquire or refresh their skills in data science and engineering and understand the latest transformations in business intelligence and data analytics, bridging the gap between technology and business management.

CONTENT

This session combines management and technological skills, addressing themes like data mining, data analytics, data quality, management systems, and business intelligence.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Innovation; data management; business intelligence; analytics.

MATERIAL

Powerpoint presentations; polls; additional materials.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Data Mining professionals; Business Intelligence experts; data science professionals.

Chapter 3. Capacity building on start-up's financial support

Masterclass #5: Essentials of innovation finance

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

This masterclass will be an overview of the key elements in innovation finance. It will incorporate an introduction to and/or recap of material from other elements in the academy program, focusing on integrating and contextualizing the material on financing.

Participants will complete the masterclass with a lexicon of key innovation financing terms. They will be able to match projects with relevant funding sources and support them in developing a financial plan. They will be able to map the fundamental sources of finance within an ecosystem and identify what will be needed to access them.

CONTENT

Seed and pre-seed investment tools. Loans. VC and Angel Investment. Investment rounds. A primer on investment terms and requirements. Grants. Impact Investing. Microcredit. Crowdfunding. KPIs. Pitching. Valuation. Financial reporting.

This content will be presented primarily in brief with interest in providing introduction and context rather than thorough information, which is presented in other modules.

THEMATIC FOCUS

The main areas covered will include the role played by financing and funding in innovative projects. There will be an overview of traditional financing, alongside an introduction to alternative financing methods. Alongside the various financing options available to innovative projects, a few fundamentals of accessing them will be introduced.

MATERIAL

Powerpoints, Case Studies, Canvases and Realia (such as term sheets and financial documents from genuine investments). Participants will be asked to fill in and reflect on some materials during the masterclass.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

The facilitator should have a thorough command of innovation financing, potentially having worked as a CFO within a start-up, with an M&A or VC firm, or in an advisory role with an incubator or accelerator. A university professor may also be appropriate, though ideally with hands-on experience.

Masterclass #6: Financing DIHs

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

This class will be a review, contextualizing and introducing the material from other academy components regarding the funding opportunities available to DIHs and some key practises that can help them remain viable over time.

Participants will end the masterclass with the resources and information needed to deliver a concrete business model for their DIH. This will incorporate the processes of limiting operational costs, developing revenue streams, identifying funding sources, and maintaining a network of critical actors within the ecosystem.

CONTENT

Funding models and revenue streams for DIH management. Sources of subsidized finance. Impact investing. Bootstrapping. Fundamentals of managerial accounting. Developing a network or ecosystem of financing sources.

As with the other masterclass, all of these elements will be presented, focusing on providing an introduction and context, with deeper learning being presented in other elements of the academy.

THEMATIC FOCUS

The core of the class will be equipping DIH managers to organize their DIHs' finances successfully. This will come in three areas: durable funding sources from operations. Second, viable sources of outside and internal financial support. Third, best practices for financial management within a DIH.

MATERIAL

Powerpoint presentations. Canvases. Best practices and case studies. Material such as the Creative Hubkit or content from Afrilabs, which can be applied outside the masterclass as guidebooks.

Participants, especially those who have engaged with other elements of the academy program, will be encouraged to bring in and present their own stories, engaging with their specific circumstances as part of the course program.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Ideally, the facilitator should have worked with a DIH and meta-level, analyzing DIHs or managing a network. If they have experience doing so within the African context, that is advantageous.

Chapter 4. Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women

Masterclass #7: Gender-lens Finance – Bridging the gender finance gap

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

Access to finance is one of the key challenges women entrepreneurs face, hindering the development of inclusive innovation ecosystems that can benefit society. In this masterclass, participants will understand the gender finance gap and how the gender-lens finance ecosystem is working to address them. They will get an introduction to the gender lens finance landscape and approaches and acquire tools to enable their DIHs to better support women entrepreneurs to access finance.

Learning outcome: Understand gender-lens finance landscape and approaches and better support women entrepreneurs accessing finance.

CONTENT

Review the gender-lens finance landscape (including stats and figures, how the sector has emerged, key actors and motivation). Gain a foundation in gender-lens investment - tools and approaches and explore the potential of capital in catalyzing gender equality and building inclusive innovation ecosystems.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Gender and finance, gender-lens investment, gender financing gap, women entrepreneurship and inclusive innovation

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, case studies, gender-lens investment tools, e.g. Gender Integration Marker and 2X challenge criteria. These materials shall be prepared by the facilitator and uploaded onto an online repository.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Gender-lens finance expert, gender-lens investor, a female entrepreneur with experience raising investment.

Masterclass #8: Building a Theory of Change

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

Every business, program, or initiative impacts (positive or negative) on society and the environment. Knowing how to measure this impact allows managers, investors, policy-makers, and implementers to make informed and better decisions to enhance and strengthen programs that improve lives or modify or reassign resources of those programs that are not achieving their objectives.

This masterclass offers participants a unique opportunity to learn tools and apply impact management and measurement. It will provide a deep dive into the Theory of change approach to monitoring impact.

Learning objective: Understand why measuring impact is relevant, gain familiarity with the Theory of change approach and learn how to develop one for their organization or initiative.

CONTENT

Why measuring impact is important and where and when it can help DIHs, impact measurement methodologies, building a Theory of Change

THEMATIC FOCUS

Impact strategy and management, Theory of Change, Monitoring, Learning and Evaluation

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, case studies, impact measurement tools and methodologies, e.g. Theory of Change. These materials shall be prepared by the facilitator and uploaded onto an online repository.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Impact strategy and management expert, Organization manager with Theory of change experience.

Conclusion

This document presents the structure and content of 8 masterclasses foreseen to be developed within the AfriConEU project, particularly within the Capacity Building for African DIHs Flagship Programme. This programme comprises four subprogrammes in different areas to answer to different needs identified.

Each subprogramme will be delivered through a series of webinars, workshops, masterclasses and additional materials such as videos, case studies, readings, etc.

Nevertheless, these stand-alone activities must be perceived as a whole programme, so it was essential to design them before implementation to keep them aligned and similarly structured. D3.1 explained the rationale behind the choice of topics.

This document should be perceived as open and flexible, enabling the implementation trainers to adapt the content and format. Trainers may change some content and suggest further interactive activities, provided preserved the overall structure.

It is crucial to analyze this document together with D3.1, D3.2, D3.3., and D3.4.